

Learning Relationships between Separate Audio Tracks for Creative Applications

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Abstract

This paper presents the first step in a research project situated within the field of musical agents. The objective is to achieve, through training, the tuning of the desired musical relationship between a live musical input and a real-time generated musical output, through the curation of a database of separated tracks. We propose an architecture integrating a symbolic decision module capable of learning and exploiting musical relationships from such musical corpus. We detail an offline implementation of this architecture employing Transformers as the decision module, associated with a perception module based on Wav2Vec 2.0, and concatenative synthesis as audio renderer. We present a quantitative evaluation of the decision module's ability to reproduce learned relationships extracted during training. We demonstrate that our decision module can predict a coherent track B when conditioned by its corresponding "guide" track A, based on a corpus of paired tracks (A, B).

1 Introduction

1.1 Problematic: tuning the relationship between inputs and outputs in Musical Agents

The present work is placed in the context of a broader project within the field of Musical Agents (MA), defined by Tatar and Pasquier (2018) as "[agents] that partially or completely automate musical creative tasks". Our long term objective is to achieve, through training, the desired tuning between a live musical input — captured via a machine listening module — and a real-time generated musical output, through the curation of a database of separated tracks. Its applications and areas of investigation are considered in both compositional and improvisational contexts. The architecture we consider is composed of: an *action* module responsible for musical synthesis guided by a *perception*

module implementing machine listening techniques to extract information from a performer’s playing on stage, and a *decision* module creating a mapping from perception to action.

Our approach is closely related to and inspired by earlier performance-driven MA(s). *ImproteK* (Nika et al., 2017a) is a reactive MA designed for live improvisation. *Somax* (Borg et al., 2022) introduces long-term planning capabilities through symbolic scenarios. *MASOM* (Tatar and Pasquier, 2017) and *SpireMuse* (Thelle and Pasquier, 2021) focus on live improvisation, incorporating affective dimensions into their machine listening. *tiNNbre* (Bolzoni et al., 2021) integrates neural networks into its decision module. Lastly, *Construction III* offers a performance-driven environment that leverages transformative and sequenced techniques (Rowe, 1992). All these agents implement their action module through corpus-based concatenative synthesis.¹ This technique employs a musical corpus stored in memory, composed of pairs of (segment, label), i.e. (content, symbol), to generate audio.

Particularly, *Dicy2* (Nika et al., 2017b), our action module (see Section 4.3), is a *scenario*-based MA combining the reactive-listening of *Somax* and the long-term scenario planning of *ImproteK*. *Dicy2* utilizes concurrent dynamic calls to symbolic scenarios, i.e. sequence of symbols, to generate audio with corpus-based concatenative synthesis. The scenario can be generated from the audio analysis of a musician’s play for real-time improvisation, or specified during offline music composition. This system learns temporal relationships within its corpus and, when providing a scenario, it generates the optimal sequence of content.

During generation, the decision module selects the segments in the corpus to be played. In general, this selection is primarily based on a combination of probabilistic models and pattern matching, with the objective of creating an optimal direct mapping between perception and action.

Usually, the perception module implements real-time audio stream analysis based on audio descriptors, such as pitch, spectral centroid, MFCCs. While classic audio descriptors are interpretable, they are limited in their ability to encode high-level musical information (Natsiou and O’Leary, 2021).

To summarize, MAs generally make use of matching rules between the generated signal and input signal. This implies the specification by hand of the musical behaviour of the agent, i.e., the explicit definition of the audio description and pre-defined scenarios. Though this offers a lot of possibilities, this could be a limitation for more complex relationships. This paper addresses the possibility to automatically learn musical relationships from a set of examples, substituting pre-defined specifications with behaviours directly learned from examples. This is done by exploring the capacities of state-of-the-art neural networks architectures both in the field of audio and music processing, as described in the following section. Ultimately, we aim at expanding the customizability and the versatility of existing MAs.

1.2 Our Approach: tuning Musical Agents’ responses through examples

Our motivation is to extend both the perception and decision modules. To improve Musical Agents’ response mechanism we decide to, first, implement the perception module with neural audio encoders to represent the audio signals with high-level musical information, and secondly, integrating a decision module capable of formulating responses based on learned relationships between separate musical tracks on a symbolic level. Additionally, we propose a novel task for the decision module focused on learning correspondences between inputs and outputs through example-based training.

Specifically, we propose to evaluate the ability of such decision module to learn and generate coherent symbolic relationships based on a corpus of paired tracks (A, B) using what we call a *re-generation* task. The goal is not to assess expressive or creative output *per se*, but to quantitatively measure the model’s capacity to learn and generate similar structural relationship between symbolic representations of separate tracks. While creative generation ultimately requires subjective evaluation, this re-generation task provides an initial, objective assessment of the decision’s capacity to learn and generalize musical relationships.

This article presents the general framework of the project, the proposed methodology, and an initial quantitative evaluation based on this re-generation task.

¹With the exception of *tiNNbre v2*, which generates audio through a Griffin-Lim re-synthesis algorithm (Griffin and Lim, 1984).

The present work proposes the following contributions to the field of Musical Metacreation, Musical Agents, and AI Creativity:

- The formalization of a high-level architecture for relationship-driven MA(s).
- An offline implementation of this architecture using Deep Learning for both perception and decision-making components.
- The design of a quantitative evaluation framework based on a re-generation task to assess the decision module’s ability to internalize musical relationships.

In the following, applications of Deep Learning in music are presented in Section 2. Then the high-level architecture of the proposed Musical Agent is formalized in Section 3. The proposed implementation of this architecture is detailed in section 4. Section 5 presents the methodology applied during this research: dataset curation, training procedure, evaluation protocol, and other relevant details. The results are presented in Section 6 and discussed in section 7. Finally, key findings and future work are presented in section 8.

2 Related Work

This work lies at the intersection of Deep Learning (DL), Musical Metacreation, and more specifically, Musical Agents. Given that our approach is primarily built upon DL architectures, we begin by presenting a relevant overview of the state of the art in DL within the musical domain. The discussion is organized around two core areas: neural audio encoders, which provide a formal foundation for the technologies underpinning our perception module implementation, and generative models, which contextualize the distinctive features of our approach.

2.1 Neural audio encoders for musical Signals

Neural audio encoders aim to project audio streams into compressed vector sequences that capture relevant musical information (Liu et al., 2022). Below, we highlight key encoders adapted for musical signals. MusicBERT (Zhu et al., 2021) is a bidirectional Transformer encoder pre-trained on alignment and reconstruction tasks to learn musical structure and inter-relations across pieces. EnCodec (Défossez et al., 2023), though designed for signal compression, also serves as a powerful encoder by producing a hierarchical, quantized vector stream which has been employed in music modeling (Borsos et al., 2023a). Wav2Vec 2.0 (Baevski et al., 2020), a contrastively trained Transformer encoder for contextual audio representation, has been successfully adapted to music (Ragano et al., 2023), achieving competitive results in pitch and instrument classification compared to task-specific models, attesting for its generalization capabilities.

We propose to take advantage of such encoders to enhance the role of machine listening in the creative process. Rather than encoding the audio signal with raw audio descriptors, our perception module would encode high-level musical information so that the decision module can learn high-level musical relationships.

2.2 Generative AI for music generation

Our work is related to research on accompaniment generation systems conditioned by an audio input, namely *guiding input* or *musical context*, and systems exploiting Language Modeling approaches for music generation, i.e. using symbols/tokens to represent audio.

The field of neural audio codecs is thriving (Zeghidour et al., 2021; Défossez et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2023; Borsos et al., 2023b; Siuzdak et al., 2024), with decoders enabling high-quality music generation from token streams (e.g. RAVE (Caillon and Esling, 2021), R-VAE (Vigliensoni et al., 2022), SingSong (Donahue et al., 2023), Jukebox (Dhariwal et al., 2020) and Jukedrummer (Wu et al., 2022)). Notably, SingSong generates instrumental tracks conditioned on vocal input, adapting AudioLM (Borsos et al., 2023a) to model instrumental tokens from vocal tokens — a methodology closely related to ours, where the symbolic sequence of track A is modeled from that of track B. Transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017) have shown strong performance in symbolic music — score-based or MIDI — generation (Yu et al., 2022; Ren et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2018), and several works successfully combine them with audio codecs to generate audio (Copet et al., 2024; Rouard et al.,

2025; Lin et al., 2023). Diff-A-Riff (Nistal et al., 2025) offers conditional accompaniment generation via a dual conditioning scheme: musical context and/or direct control through textual prompts or audio references, enabling fine-grained guidance over the generated accompaniment.

The architecture we propose below is similarly conditioned by an audio input. Its distinctive feature is that it focuses not on generating audio, but on producing a high-level symbolic specification for audio generation. It uses deep learning to learn and exploit relationships between symbolic sequences extracted from curated paired audio files to generate specifications to send to a corpus-based synthesis engine that will produce the actual musical response.

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3 Architecture

In the following Section, we propose a high-level architecture of a relationship-based Musical Agent and its mathematical formulation. This architecture is composed of three key components. A **Perception** module that converts a continuous audio signal into a sub-sampled discrete, i.e. symbolic, sequence. A **Decision** module that learns and exploits symbolic relationships between symbolic sequences. An **Action** module that converts a symbolic sequence back into audio.

Figure 1 depicts the difference between an offline and online framework for Musical Agents. A finalized Musical Agent for real-time performance will involve a perception module based on machine listening to extract information from an audio stream over an interval $[T-\Delta;T]$ in order to provide a symbolic representation that will be used by the decision module to generate a symbolic specification of the music to be generated over an interval $[T;T+\Delta]$. In this paper, we focus on the decision module and consider an offline architecture where the audio control stream is an audio file, and where the symbolic representation provided by the perception module over an interval $[T-\Delta;T]$ serves as input to the decision module to generate a symbolic specification of the audio to be played over the same interval $[T-\Delta;T]$.

Figure 1: Online vs. offline framework for relationship-based Musical Agents.

The general offline framework consists in specifying the musical response, noted $\vec{y} = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{T_y}]$, corresponding to a guiding input $\vec{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{T_x}]$, with $T_y \neq T_x$ in general. So the function f realized by the agent is defined as: $y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{T_y} = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{T_x})$. This function is modeled by the conditional probability $p(\vec{y}|\vec{x})$ defined in Equation 1. The response \vec{y} is generated auto-regressively by predicting the probability of the t -th sample (y_t) conditioned by previous samples ($\vec{y}_{<t}$) and the guiding input (\vec{x}). It is noteworthy that this probability is computationally intractable since it requires access to all previous samples of $\vec{y}_{<t}$ and \vec{x} , further validating the choice of modeling musical relationships on a subsampled, symbolic scale.

$$p(\vec{y}|\vec{x}) = \prod_{t=1}^{T_y} p(y_t|\vec{y}_{<t}, \vec{x}) \quad (1)$$

3.1 Perception: converting audio to a sequence of symbols

The Perception module should capture complex musical information, beyond a simple choice of audio descriptors. Musical relationships, as they are approached in this work, are modeled through a symbolic alphabet. For this matter, the Perception module also converts the audio stream into a sequence of symbols. This layer of symbolic abstraction is achieved by means of a discrete musical alphabet. Obviously, the purpose of this alphabet should correspond to high-level classes of musical equivalences in order to allow the Decision module to extract relations between symbolic sequences.

Equation 2 describes the mathematical function realized by the Perception module : an audio sequence \vec{x} of sampling rate F_s is sub-sampled from $F_s \times T_x$ to N_x , with $N_x \ll F_s \times T_x$, and projected into a quantized space composed of K vectors (c_i). K corresponds to the size of the musical alphabet, and the $c_i \in \mathbb{R}^D$ are vectors corresponding to the musical classes, i.e. tokens. For simplicity's sake, we write $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\} = C_K$, also called *codebook*.

$$\begin{aligned} P : \vec{x} &\longmapsto P(\vec{x}) = \vec{x}_q = [x_{q_1}, x_{q_2}, \dots, x_{q_{N_x}}] \\ \mathbb{R}^{F_s \times T} &\longrightarrow \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\}^{N_x} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Decision: learning and exploiting symbolic relationships

The musical relationships at the heart of this research are approached at a symbolic level. With the symbolic abstraction layer provided by P , these relationships are expressed through the relationships between two symbolic sequences extracted from two audio sequences. In the proposed formulation, this relationship between symbolic sequences is learned by the Decision module. During inference, the Decision module generates a *symbolic specification* — given a conditioning input \vec{x}_q — of what must be played by the Action module.

The symbolic specification is generated by an autoregressive model D formalized by Equation 3. D predicts at each frame t the probabilities over the K tokens of the musical alphabet, given the previous token vectors $\vec{y}_{q < t} \in C_K^{t-1}$ in the sequence and a conditioning sequence \vec{x}_q . Then, a specific token amongst the ones with high probability can be selected for the next iteration.

$$\begin{aligned} D : \vec{x}_q, \vec{y}_{q < t} &\longmapsto D(\vec{y}_{q < t}, \vec{x}_q) = p(\mathbf{y}_{qt} | \vec{y}_{q < t}, \vec{x}_q) \\ C_K^{N_x} \times C_K^{t-1} &\longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^K \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

3.3 Action: converting a symbolic specification to audio

The Action module allows the agent to interact with its user and environment. This module allows switching from the symbolic domain to the audio domain: generating the audio signal $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ corresponding to the symbolic specification \vec{y}_q given by D . There are many approaches to synthesizing or generating audio from a sequence of symbolic classes. However, what is expected of the Action module is to convert a sub-sampled symbolic sequence to its corresponding up-sampled audio-rate signal.

Equation 4 describes the mathematical function realized by the Action module : given a symbolic specification \vec{y}_q (expressed as a sequence of tokens or their corresponding class IDs), A converts a sequence of discrete values back into its corresponding audio signal $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$.

$$\begin{aligned} A : \vec{y}_q &\longmapsto A(\vec{y}_q) = \hat{\mathbf{y}} \\ C_K^{N_y} \text{ or } [0; K-1]^{N_y} &\longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{F_s * T_y} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

4 Model implementation

This section describes a specific implementation of the high-level architecture for a Musical Agent capable of generating musical responses based on relationships learned from a corpus of separate tracks². Following the guidelines of Section 3, Figure 2 depicts the implementation of the three

²Code and audio examples can be found at <https://github.com/ircam-ismm/learning-from-paired-tracks>.

components enabling the generation of such responses: a Perception module encoding audio streams into discrete musical representations on which symbolic musical relationships will be learned, an Action module converting a symbolic sequence back into audio, and finally, the Decision module which learns and exploits symbolic relationships between related tracks enabling the generation of musical responses extending beyond a matching rule between input and output.

Figure 2: Overview of the proposed relationship-based Musical Agent architecture. The pipeline is divided into three modules. The Perception module encodes an audio input \vec{x} into a sub-sampled, quantized symbolic sequence \vec{x}_q using a pre-trained encoder, a temporal condenser, and a vector quantizer. The Decision module generates a symbolic response \vec{y}_q based on \vec{x}_q through a sequence decoder and token selection. Finally, the Action module reconstructs audio from \vec{y}_q via corpus-based concatenative synthesis. The synthesis corpus is a user-defined audio file segmented and encoded through the same Perception module.

The overall processing pipeline consists of:

1. The audio input, i.e. guide or musical context, \vec{x} , provided as a waveform, is segmented into pieces of uniform or variable size. In the following, only uniform segmentation is studied.
2. The Perception module encodes the whole sequence and, in the sub-sampled latent space, each segment is condensed to extract the quantified representation \vec{x}_q .
3. \vec{x}_q is processed by the Decision module to generate the symbolic specification \vec{y}_q .
4. The Action module uses corpus based concatenative synthesis, and exploits this specification to construct the musical response, \hat{y} .

The internal structure of each module will be detailed in the following.

4.1 Perception: Wav2Vec2.0 as a music encoder

The Perception module is responsible for transforming the audio signal into relevant and discrete musical representations to constitute the musical alphabet on which the relationships are learned. It consists of a self-supervised and pre-trained model (*Encoder*) that extracts a contextualized representation rich in musical information, a *Condenser* module to limit the computational load of the Decision module and assign a single vector to each segment, and a vector quantization (*VQ*) module to assign an item of the musical alphabet to each element of the sub-sampled sequence.

A Wav2Vec 2.0 model pre-trained on music (Ragano et al., 2023), herein named $wav2vec_{mus}$, is chosen as the encoding model. The *Condenser* consists of a simple temporal average since it does

not need any training. The VQ is implemented using a k-means algorithm trained offline for each model configuration, i.e. dataset, duration of audio segment, and vocabulary size.

The whole audio sequence \vec{x} is first encoded by $wav2vec_{mus}$ to extract a contextualized latent representation, then each sub-sampled segment is condensed on the time axis by the *Condenser*, and finally quantized by the VQ to generate the symbolic sequence \vec{x}_q and its corresponding labels; respectively *Tokens* and *Class IDs* in Figure 2.

4.2 Decision: Transformers generating symbolic specifications

The Decision module is in charge of learning and exploiting those symbolic relations between separate musical tracks, and generating a symbolic specification. This symbolic specification is what allows for the formulation of musical responses possibly beyond the scope of matching.

In order to achieve this objective, the Decision module is composed of two elements: a sequence generator (*Decoder*) and a token selection algorithm (*Token Selection*).

Since the main objective of the Decision is to predict a sequence of symbols (akin to tokens), the choice of implementing it through a Transformer-decoder architecture seemed natural. The Transformer-decoder outputs a sequence of probabilities over the musical alphabet following Equation 3, conditioned by \vec{x}_q the tokens of the encoded audio input and the previously generated tokens ($\vec{y}_{q<t}$). Then the selection algorithm simply selects an item from the vocabulary given its probability distribution. There are multiple choices of decoding scheme, here a top-P nucleus sampling (Holtzman et al., 2020) was preferred.

4.3 Action: Dicy2 as a compositional tool for offline audio generation

The action module of the proposed implementation is based on Dicy2 and concatenative synthesis. The action module receives as input 1) a symbolic specification resulting from the Decision module, 2) a user-defined corpus in which audio segments will be searched and rearranged to perform concatenative synthesis.

The corpus on which the Dicy2 agent trains is extracted from an audio file processed by the Perception module, and the scenario corresponds to the output of the Decision module, i.e. the symbolic specification. The symbols and contents correspond, respectively, to the class IDs from the Perception analysis, and the segment indexes of the audio segments.

When presented with a symbolic specification, Dicy2 generates an optimal sequence of segment indexes from the audio corpus. The musical response is then constructed by concatenating the audio segments corresponding to the slice indexes returned by Dicy2.

In the context of an action module based on concatenative synthesis, generating audio from a symbolic specification requires that the predicted labels *exist* within the corpus' labels. To address this, we introduce a method called *constrained generation*, which guides the decoding algorithm by favoring the selection of labels present in the corpus. Specifically, since the corpus is given as a parameter, the existing labels are available. This information can be given to the decision module and if any of those labels are present in the top-P selection, sample from them. This effectively improves the probability to generate symbols from the corpus and avoiding non-existing symbols that translate to silent audio segments with corpus-based concatenative synthesis. While it improves the portion of correct matches, it can lead to lower diversity in the symbolic specification and therefore more repetition in the musical response.

5 Methodology

5.1 Dataset

In order to enable the learning of musical relationships, it is essential that the utilized dataset contains multi-stem mixes. The underlying argument posits that, within a mix, all the stems are inherently interconnected, thereby rendering it possible to extract musical relationships from these mixes.

Two datasets were used: MoisesDB (Pereira et al., 2023), comprising 240 tracks (~60h of stems) of contemporary music with 11 instruments, and the proprietary MICA dataset, with 179 tracks

(~50h of stems) of free improvisations featuring duos and trios. These contrasting music corpora allow the exploration of different musical relationships. Given the preponderance of Western pop music in MoisesDB, which is commensurate with tonal music, it can be posited that the predominant relationships in this corpus pertain to melody and harmony. Conversely, the MICA dataset is constituted of a series of non-idiomatic improvisations, which primarily encompass relationships that are predicated on interactions involving density and energy.

To focus on narrative and discursive interaction, rhythmic elements (e.g., drums, percussion) and effects were excluded, as they do not serve the same musical function and could bias the model toward another types of relationship mainly defined by the synchronicity between musical elements.

We use an 80-10-10 split for training, validation, and test sets, with audio tracks segmented into 15-second windows with 5-second overlaps. During training, a random pair of stems (A, B) is extracted from the original mix. Therefore, no unique mapping from one track to another is forced, the decision should learn symbolic relationships from a corpus-specific scale relationships. In other words we consider high-level common relationships occurring between *all* pairs of the corpus. This is thus in contrast to track-specific relationships, which are relationships from a pair of input and output stem, i.e. paired instruments relationships.

It should be noted that the size of the datasets are relatively small for the type of learning task we consider. In comparison, Diff-A-Riff (Nistal et al., 2025) trains on 1M pairs of input and target audio (equivalent to 2.7K hours), SingSong (Donahue et al., 2023) also trains its model on 1M audio inputs (equivalent to 46K hours), and MusicGen-Stem (Rouard et al., 2025) leverage 17K hours of instrumental audio. In our case, the datasets can be smaller since we do not synthesize audio from the symbolic specification. The effect of the dataset size will be discussed in Section 7.2.

5.2 Learning musical relationships

The objective of the proposed Musical Agent, and more specifically its decision module, is to learn musical relationships from a corpus of separated tracks to enable the generation of responses exploiting these learned relationships. The methodology employed in this paper to learn such relationships consists in exploiting multi-stem datasets to extract general musical relationships specific to each musical corpora. Please note that the Decision module is not designed to learn track-specific relationships.

Figure 3 depicts the learning process of musical relationships within 2 stems. The Perception module encodes both stems coming from the original pair (A, B), and the Decision’s objective is to predict the classes associated with tokens of Stem B from the sequence of tokens of Stem A. This objective is achieved by implementing a cross-entropy loss between the predicted classes and the classes from the encoding of the original Stem B. In accordance with the principles outlined by AudioLM, we freeze the Perception module in charge of *tokenizing* the audio stream (Borsos et al., 2023a). The Decision module has 6 transformer-decoder layers, 12 heads, model dimension of 768, feedforward dimension of 2048, and 0.1 dropout. We employ Adam (Kingma and Ba, 2015) optimizer with batch size of 24, $\text{lr} = 1e^{-6}$, $\beta = (0.9, 0.999)$, weight decay = $1e^{-5}$, and trained until convergence. To reduce Exposure Bias, an exponential decay scheduled sampling training is implemented (Bengio et al., 2015). Preliminary experiments proved that it effectively improves the generation quality.

This study focuses exclusively on uniform segmentation of audio, a choice that is made to facilitate synchronization issues between input and generated output audios. Three sizes of segmentation windows are employed: 250 ms, 350 ms and 500 ms. This choice of uniform segmentation rather than *event*-related segmentation is sub-optimal for the quality on the final audio rendering. As our primary focus in this paper concerns the proposition about learning and exploiting symbolic relationships, the limitation due to uniform segmentation will not be further evaluated and will only be investigated in future works.

The proposed architecture utilizes a musical alphabet or vocabulary, the size of which constitutes a pivotal hyper-parameter. The present study investigates therefore three vocabulary sizes: 16, 64, and 256. This size exerts a substantial influence on the vocabulary’s granularity, manifesting in two correlated effects. Firstly, modeling symbolic musical relationships becomes more manageable with a limited vocabulary. Conversely, diversity in relationships is diminished.

Figure 3: Training procedure for learning symbolic musical relationships.

5.3 Evaluating learned musical relationships

This section presents the evaluation methodology employed during this work. Our hypothesis is that the capacity of the decision module to exploit learned relationships can be measured through a *re-generation* task. This re-generation task consists in evaluating the decision module’s ability to generate the symbolic representation of track B, conditioned on track A — (one of) the track(s) it was originally paired with in the dataset.³ This task is evaluated through two quantitative measures: *True Positive Percentage* and *Longest Common Prefix*.

True Positive Percentage (TPP), expressed in Equation 5, is simply the count of True Positive (TP) predictions divided by the total length of the ground truth (GT) sequence. In this context, TPP is employed to quantify the similarity between the predicted symbolic sequence B' , generated from stem A, and the original symbolic sequence of B from the paired stems (A, B).

$$\text{TruePositivePercentage} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \{1 \mid \text{pred}[i] = \text{GT}[i]\}}{N} \cdot 100, \text{ where } N = \text{length}(\text{GT}) \quad (5)$$

To complement TPP’s insights on the decision’s performances, we introduce the *Longest Common Prefix* (LCP) measure to compute the lengths of correct prefixes between the predicted symbolic sequence B' , generated from stem A, and the symbolic sequence of stem B (stem A’s original pair). This metric is inspired by sequence matching in bioinformatics (Gusfield, 1997), in particular the Longest Common Factor (Crochemore, 1987; Crochemore et al., 2008) (LCF), which searches for subsequences maximizing an alignment score. LCP differs from LCF by requiring the two sequences to be aligned in time when computing the longest prefix, which is essential in this re-generation task. LCP returns a list of common prefix lengths for each position in the sequence, which provide complementary insights on the performances of the symbolic re-generation task.

Let $S, T \in [0; K - 1]^*$ be two strings of length n , and let $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n - 1\}$. We define the Longest Common Prefix between the suffixes $S_i = S[i..]$ and $T_i = T[i..]$ as:

$$\text{LCP}_i(S, T) = \max \{ \ell \in \mathbb{N} \mid i + \ell \leq n, \forall k < \ell, S_i[k] = T_i[k] \}$$

6 Results

The results of the re-generation task are presented below, measured quantitatively using True Positive Percentage (TPP) and Longest Common Prefix (LCP). Since this task has never been published with similar framework, no baseline model is available for comparison. Nevertheless, it is worth

³We remind again that this pairing of track (A, B) is not unique: during training, the decision learns the mapping from A to B, from B to A and all other combinations of mappings depending on the number of stems in the original mix.

introducing a baseline, where symbolic sequences are generated by randomly sampling from the entire alphabet. Given that the task focuses on learning relationships at the corpus level rather than track-specific ones, perfect re-generation of stem B from its originally paired stem A is not expected. However, this task should demonstrate the decision’s ability to at least partially learn relationships between paired tracks.

The p parameter of nucleus sampling is set to 0.8 for all configurations. Both the model and random baseline are evaluated with and without the constrained generation (see 4.3) for TPP measures, and only under constrained generation for LCP measures.

Figure 4 presents boxplots of the TPP distributions for the MoisesDB and MICA datasets under the standard setup, while Figure 5 shows the same metric under constrained generation. Different alphabet sizes are grouped by color, with gray representing the random baseline. On the x -axis, model configurations follow the convention {segment duration}s_A{alphabet size}. Overall, all configurations outperform random baselines. Figure 4 shows better performances for small alphabet size, but distributions presents greater variance. While in Figure 5, Constrained generation appears to enhance the performance of model predictions across configurations, particularly for larger alphabet sizes. For this matter, only this setup is considered for the LCP evaluation.

Figures 6a and 6b show the LCP values per sequence position for, respectively, MoisesDB and MICA datasets under the constrained generation setting. Both figures present the nine configurations, ordered by alphabet (y-axis) and segmentation size (x-axis). The blue lines represent the mean LCP with standard deviation in light blue, while the black lines show the random baseline for comparison. The red line indicates the maximum possible LCP at each position, calculated as $L - x$, where L is the sequence length and x the position. A symmetric logarithmic scale is used to better visualize low LCP values and highlight small variations across the sequence. In general, LCPs tend to exceed the random baseline, yet they continue to demonstrate difficulty in approaching the maximum value.

7 Discussion

This section offers key interpretations of the results presented above. We begin with synthesized analysis of our results on the re-generation task in the beginning of 7.1, prior to a per-metric analysis in Sections 7.1.1 and 7.1.2, which sheds light on several aspects of the re-generation task. This is followed by a broader discussion in Section 7.2, identifying core limitations in our current architecture and methodology, and outlining directions for future work on relationship-based responses in Musical Agents.

7.1 Re-generation task

This work explored the possibility to include learned relationships in the decision process of Musical Agents. The training of the different model configurations converged for both datasets, and the symbolic performances on the re-generation task prove that some relationships have been learned. The evaluation on each dataset leads to *True Positive Percentage* (TPP) between 10% and 20% of the learned relationships. Such percentage values, which might appear as low, was expected, since the TPP values do not take into account any specificity of the different tracks, but rather to general "musical relationships" that are emerging globally in each database. Thus, the important finding is that we can confirm such general relationship are learned, as shown by the fact that the values are significantly larger than a random generation (p -value < 0.0001). Therefore, what has been learned must be high-level, common relationships among all paired tracks, i.e. corpus-level relationships. Moreover, such learning appears in both stylistically very different datasets, MoisesDB and MICA, related to different music genre (pop/rock and free improvisation). This observation allows us to, at least partially, validate the interest of our framework. In the following sections we discuss in more details how the quantitative metrics True Positive Percentage and Longest Common Prefix are influenced by different parameters.

7.1.1 True Positive Percentage

Results show that smaller vocabularies significantly outperform random baselines, while larger vocabularies lead to a noticeable performance drop. The segmentation size appears to have little impact for the TPP. Instead, increased vocabulary size generally correlates with reduced performance,

(a) MoisesDB

(b) MICA

Figure 4: True Positive Percentage (TPP) of the re-generation task for MoisesDB (a) and MICA (b). Model configurations are grouped by alphabet size and ordered by segmentation duration. Random baseline (gray) is plotted on the right of its corresponding configuration. Mann-Whitney statistical test returns $p\text{-value} < 0.0001$ for all configurations.

(a) MoisesDB

(b) MICA

Figure 5: True Positive Percentage (TPP) of the re-generation task for MoisesDB (a) and MICA (b) under constrained generation setup. Model configurations are grouped by alphabet size and ordered by segmentation duration. Random baseline (gray) is plotted on the right of its corresponding configuration. Mann-Whitney statistical test returns $p\text{-value} < 0.0001$ for all configurations.

(a) MoisesDB

(b) MICA

Figure 6: LCP of re-generation task for MoisesDB (a) and MICA (b) under constrained generation setup. Model configurations are ordered by alphabet size (vertical axis) and segment duration (horizontal axis). Blue lines represent the mean prefix length, red lines are the maximum prefix length, and black lines represent the mean of the random baselines.

likely due to the difficulty of modeling fine-grained relationships. Interestingly, MoisesDB maintains more stable results even with larger alphabets, suggesting more coherent or consistent relationships within its corpus. Constrained Generation significantly improves the TPP for larger vocabularies by prioritizing symbols already present in the paired sequence to which it is compared to. On average, this subset represents only $6 \pm 2\%$ ⁴ of the vocabulary in the A256 configuration, effectively restricting predictions to a small portion of the total vocabulary and thereby increasing the likelihood of correct matches. However, the large variance observed across configurations (as shown by the wide boxplots) indicates a pronounced variability in the model’s performances.

To complement our results, we also report an entropy measure of the generated sequences to quantify the diversity of the sequences in Figures 7 and 8 of the Annexes. Generally, diversity increases with alphabet size, an expected result since a larger alphabet implies larger maximum entropy.

7.1.2 Longest Common Prefix

Models which are closer to the red baseline (max) indicate better results and LCP analysis shows that our results outperform random baselines, which is a good indicator of the success of our approach. These results remain difficult to be fully explained, nevertheless we propose below some interpretations.

First, while results outperform random baseline, the prefix lengths remain low, indicating difficulty in anticipating future tokens.

We observe that the smallest segmentation window performs best for the MICA dataset, while no similar conclusion can be drawn for MoisesDB. In particular, for MICA, A64/0.25s yields the highest LCP, whereas A256/0.5s performs the worst. This suggests that small segmentation windows are better at capturing fine-grained information, likely because MICA is composed of free improvisations where information variation depends on individual notes.

In contrast, MoisesDB—composed of Western pop music, i.e., *pulsed* music—appears to require a segmentation window that aligns with the beat (pulse) of the track. While LCP shows no consistent trend across segment duration or alphabet size for MoisesDB, we find that A256/0.25s approaches the maximum LCP value, whereas A256/0.5s is only slightly better than the random baseline.

Across both datasets, we note that a large vocabulary combined with a large segmentation window performs poorly. This may indicate that encoding long audio segments with high class granularity generates incoherent or unreliable information that is more difficult to model. These findings suggest that encoded information in small segments is more reliable and easier to model, especially in datasets with fine temporal variation.

Unlike TPP, LCP shows no consistent trend across segment duration or alphabet size. Notably, strong TPP does not guarantee high LCP: the 0.25s A256 configuration yields the best and most stable LCP scores for MoisesDB, whereas the 0.5s A16 — strong in TPP — performs poorly in LCP. Although not consistent across segment durations, A256 tends to offer competitive LCP results, possibly due to lower variance in TPP and the constrained prediction space improving consistency.

Consistent LCP would suggest a model’s capacity to anticipate, a key trait for real-time musical applications where forward-looking behavior ensures coherent interaction (Nika, 2016). Further investigation is required to assess this consistency : particularly, further analysis of LCP distribution is required in order to characterize since the variance in our results does not enable to draw clear conclusions.

7.2 Limitations

First, the nature of musical relationships itself is inherently complex, thus refined learning and evaluation strategies are necessary. In particular, the metrics used for evaluation are quite strict and reflect only partially the validity of our architecture. These metrics compare the generated output to a single, fixed ground truth, which may not capture the diversity of valid outputs that could be considered "perceptively" correct. Moreover, this also limits the assessment of the model’s flexibility and its ability to generalize. Importantly, it would be necessary to evaluate qualitatively the performance of the system.

⁴Measured on the validation set

The second limitation is the combination of a small dataset with high intrinsic variability. While the accompaniment systems discussed in 2.2 benefit from large proprietary datasets, publicly available resources — especially multitrack datasets — remain scarce. MoisesDB (Pereira et al., 2023) is currently the largest multitrack dataset for pop/rock, but includes little jazz. Recent efforts such as the Jazz Trio Dataset by Cheston et al. (2024), which provides around 45 hours of multi-instrument recordings, are valuable contributions, yet the majority of available data remains heavily biased toward Western pop music (Born, 2020; Holzapfel et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the Perception module produces symbolic sequences with a class imbalance — persisting across different alphabet sizes, datasets, and segmentation durations — and sequences exhibiting long repetitions of the same token. This pattern encourages the model to overfit this repetition pattern and produce highly repetitive outputs (especially under greedy sampling strategies like $k = 1$).

Finally, the choice of uniform segmentation may also hinder the model’s performance. Incorrectly aligned segmentation windows can result in segments that lack coherence. For instance, one half of a segment might contain silence, while the other half may have musical notes. This misalignment can create issues in terms of both coherence and semantic meaning within the generated sequences. Furthermore, the presence of long notes may span across multiple tokens, emphasizing this repetition pattern in the output of the Perception module.

One of the central challenges encountered in this study lies in the complexity of the implemented architecture, which makes it difficult to interpret the results with clarity. While the Wav2Vec2.0-based Perception module may capture musical information, the nature of this information remains opaque. Without a clearer understanding of the representations encoded at this stage, it becomes particularly difficult to evaluate what kind of symbolic relationships, if any, are effectively learned by the Transformer-based Decision module. This lack of transparency hinders our ability to determine whether the model captures meaningful musical correspondences between paired tracks.

8 Conclusion and Future Works

We presented a general architecture for audio generation guided by the listening of another audio stream. We established the baseline for a learning model inferring symbolic relationships between a perception module and the output of a decision module.

To evaluate this baseline, we presented quantitative results on a re-generation task: generating a sequence using a decision module trained on a large dataset of paired tracks (A, B). Precisely, we compared the generated output to a reference track B, originally paired with A in the dataset. To move forward toward an architecture that is highly customizable via a curated user dataset, we will extend the quantitative analysis to a re-construction task aiming at reconstructing B strictly after fine-tuning of the decision module on the (A, B) pair.

Furthermore, our work will focus on what we could call *creative generalization* — namely, attempting to identify relationships comparable to those found in the training dataset between entirely different inputs and outputs. Such questions being highly subjective, they will be evaluated using qualitative methods in the context of fieldwork with musicians. This question is closely tied to the characterization of the musical dimensions encoded in the perception module we have developed, such as the similarity or proximity between classes established by our encoder. These aspects will also be examined in order to refine our loss functions by introducing notions of "prediction error quality", considering functional equivalence classes of tokens (Carsault et al., 2018).

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our gratitude to Dr. Alessandro Ragano for providing the weights of the Wav2Vec 2.0 model that was pre-trained on music.

Ethical statement

This research did not involve any human participants or animals. The datasets used in this work were accessed legally, either under open access (MoisesDB) or formal agreement of the data copyright

owners (MICA). We focused on minimizing the environmental footprint of neural network computations. The code developed for this project will be released as open-source software to ensure reproducibility. The authors report no conflicts of interest.

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A Re-generation task : diversity

Figure 7: Entropy of re-generation task for MoisesDB and MICA

Figure 8: Entropy of re-generation task for MoisesDB and MICA under constrained generation setup